

EFFECTIVENESS OF A REHABILITATION PROGRAM FOR CHILDREN BORN WITH LOW BIRTH WEIGHT

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The frequency of preterm births and the birth of low birth weight infants accounts for 4-12% of all births [1, 4, 5, 12]. Perinatal mortality among low birth weight infants is 6-10 times higher than that of infants with normal birth weight, making their care and rehabilitation a significant socio-economic challenge due to the associated high costs and disease burden [2, 6, 18, 20]. Perinatal damage to the central nervous system (CNS) unites a large group of brain damage of various causes and origins that occur during pregnancy, childbirth, and in the first days of a child's life [3, 7, 15, 19]. Severe forms of perinatal CNS damage are observed in 1.5–10% of full-term and 60–70% of premature infants [8, 10, 14]. A promising modern direction is the determination of autoantibodies to organs and tissues for preclinical diagnostics of functional and a number of organic changes in them [11, 13, 17]. Studying the level of autoantibodies to gliospecific proteins is important for understanding the mechanisms of damage to astrocytic glia and the blood-brain barrier in low-birth-weight infants, as well as for improving methods of early diagnostics of disorders of higher nervous activity and their prevention [9, 16].

Objective. To assess the effectiveness of a rehabilitation program on the physical development and health status of children born with low birth weight.

Materials and methods. A total of 70 children born with low birth weight were examined. Of these, 25 children underwent a full rehabilitation course based on our developed program (Group 1), and 45 children underwent traditional rehabilitation (Group 2). The rehabilitation program included exclusive breastfeeding in the first 6 months, continued breastfeeding up to 2 years, timely introduction of complementary foods, rational nutrition, massage, early introduction of antioxidants and metabolic agents, as well as preparations for the formation of optimal gut microflora. Physical development was assessed based on weight, length/height, and weight-for-age index (WAZ) according to WHO standards.

Results. The research findings indicated the effectiveness of the rehabilitation program. Children in Group 1 showed improvements in physical development, with weight and length-for-age surpassing the -2SD threshold earlier than those in Group 2 ($p < 0.05$). The median age for boys in Group 1 was 15 months, and for girls, it was 11 months. Children who completed the comprehensive rehabilitation course had significantly fewer illnesses in their first and second years of life, with no cases of rickets or anemia. Acute respiratory infections occurred 1-2 times a year, totaling 8%, compared to 3-4 times a year in 9.1% of children in the comparison group.

The recommended rehabilitation program led to earlier achievement of standards for weight, length/height, and body mass index (BMI) for age, along with improvements in somatic pathology indicators. This included a 5.7-fold reduction in the frequency of anemia, a 3.4-fold reduction in functional gastrointestinal disorders in the first year, and a 2.3-fold reduction in the second year of life.

In conclusion, implementing a comprehensive rehabilitation program involving early intervention for children born with low birth weight contributes to improved physical development, reduced somatic pathology, increased resilience to adverse effects, ultimately leading to better overall health and development of the child.

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